

A GENERAL STRAIN-BASED FAILURE CRITERION FOR FIBRE-REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Orthotropic, fibre-reinforced composite laminae under biaxial plane stress loading conditions are considered. A new strain-based strength criterion for such laminae is proposed. This failure criterion, which is cast in parametric form, is completely general. The advantages of our failure theory are discussed, and an example of application is presented.

KEYWORDS: Composites, Paperboard, Orthotropic laminae, Biaxial strength, Failure criterion.

1. INTRODUCTION

Because of their high specific strengths, advanced fibre-reinforced composite materials are rapidly emerging as new structural materials for replacing metal alloys in numerous engineering applications. These composites are often built-up from plies of unidirectional or bi-directional (and thus orthotropic) laminae stacked together in prescribed orientations. Other natural materials, such as wood and its derivatives, also display similar anisotropic behaviour and have important practical applications. To utilize these composites to their full potential, it is essential to be able to predict their strengths for the complex loading conditions to which they might be subjected. This is usually accomplished using classical lamination theory together with the strength properties of the individual laminae. Over the years, many failure theories have been proposed for characterizing the strength properties of composite laminae under complex states of biaxial stress and strain. These various failure theories have been reviewed by Rowlands (1) and Labossière and Neale (2).

Among the many failure theories that have been suggested, the maximum stress and strain criteria are the most employed in practice (3). This is due mainly to their simplicity, rather than their ability to accurately represent experimental data. Another theory widely used is the quadratic form of the tensor polynomial criterion of Tsai and Wu (4), which can be written as follows:

$$F_i \sigma_i + F_{ij} \sigma_i \sigma_j = 1 \quad (1)$$

Here F_i and F_{ij} are strength parameters and $i, j = 1, \dots, 6$. For plane stress conditions, this criterion represents an ellipsoid in the three-dimensional stress space $\sigma_1 - \sigma_2 - \tau_{12}$ ($= \sigma_6$) (4). When the 1- and 2-directions are aligned with the fibre directions, this reduces to

$$F_1 \sigma_1 + F_2 \sigma_2 + F_{11} \sigma_1^2 + F_{22} \sigma_2^2 + F_6 \tau_{12}^2 + 2F_{12} \sigma_1 \sigma_2 = 1 \quad (2)$$

The strength parameters F_i and F_{ii} (no summation) are usually determined from uniaxial tensile and compressive tests in the fibre directions, and pure shear tests. The interaction parameter F_{12} is evaluated from a biaxial test, and its magnitude must be constrained to ensure closure of the strength envelope (4). Different methods (5) have been proposed for the determination of the interaction factor, but there is no general agreement yet on the best method. These methods can lead to different values of the interaction parameter, and consequently lead to different failure envelopes (5).

A general *stress-based* failure theory for composite laminae under biaxial plane stress conditions has recently been formulated by Labossière and Neale (6). This approach consists of describing the failure surface, in stress space, in parametric form. A typical failure surface in the three-dimensional stress space $\sigma_1 - \sigma_2 - \tau_{12}$ is shown in Fig. 1, where again the 1- and 2-directions correspond to the axes of orthotropy. The position of any point on this failure surface can be identified as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1 &= \rho(\alpha, \phi) \cos \alpha \sin \phi \\ \sigma_2 &= \rho(\alpha, \phi) \sin \alpha \sin \phi \\ \tau_{12} &= \rho(\alpha, \phi) \cos \phi \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $\rho(\alpha, \phi)$ is the magnitude of the radius vector from the origin of the system of axes to the failure point for a given stress combination. The angle α locates the relative position of this vector with respect to the σ_1 -axis in the $\sigma_1 - \sigma_2$ plane, and ϕ indicates its angular position relative to the τ_{12} axis.

The essence of the Labossière-Neale parametric theory consists of determining the function $\rho(\alpha, \phi)$, for the lamina in question, that best describes the experimental data. Any appropriate function of the angles α and ϕ that ensures closure of the failure surface and satisfies the symmetry of the surface with respect to the plane $\tau_{12} = 0$ is admissible (6). It has been shown that the criterion is quite general in that it encompasses all previously proposed criteria. Furthermore, it is easy to implement in design applications.

In this investigation we again limit attention to orthotropic fibre-reinforced laminae under in-plane biaxial loading conditions. The parametric approach discussed above is

Fig. 1 Parametric failure surface in three-dimensional stress space.

used to formulate a general *strain-based* failure theory for such materials. One reason for describing failure surfaces in terms of strains, rather than stresses, is that strains are more immediately measurable during complex tests. Moreover, in strain space the failure surface of a laminate is not influenced by the thicknesses of the individual laminae. Also, the experimental determination of the characteristic strength parameters is more direct with a strain-based failure theory, as strains are more readily measurable than stresses.

2. A STRAIN-BASED PARAMETRIC FAILURE THEORY FOR ORTHOTROPIC LAMINAE

By analogy with the criterion of Labossière and Neale (6), the failure surface is described parametrically in three-dimensional strain space $\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2 - \epsilon_6$ as follows (Fig. 2):

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_1 &= h(\alpha, \phi) \cos \alpha \sin \phi \\ \epsilon_2 &= h(\alpha, \phi) \sin \alpha \sin \phi \\ \epsilon_6 &= h(\alpha, \phi) \cos \phi\end{aligned}\quad (4)$$

where the 1- and 2-directions are again chosen to coincide with the axes of orthotropy. In Equation (4), $h(\alpha, \phi)$ is the magnitude of the radius vector from the origin of the system of axes to the failure point for a given strain combination. The angle α locates the relative position of this vector with respect to the ϵ_1 -axis in the $\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2$ plane, and ϕ indicates its angular position relative to the ϵ_6 -axis.

In Fig. 2, the points on the failure surface corresponding to the common uniaxial tension (ϵ_i^{ut}), uniaxial compression (ϵ_i^{uc}), and pure shear (ϵ^s) tests are indicated. In addition, the plane strain tension (ϵ_i^{pt}) and compression (ϵ_i^{pc}) states define the points where the

failure surface intersects the ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 axes in the plane $\epsilon_6 = 0$. For orthotropic laminae the failure surface must be symmetrical about the plane $\epsilon_6 = 0$. This is to ensure that a lamina with material axes oriented at an angle $+\theta$ and subjected to an applied positive shear strain, and one with $-\theta$ and a negative shear strain, will exhibit the same ultimate failure strain.

The new parametric failure criterion is described by the particular function $h(\alpha, \phi)$. Various functions of the angles α and ϕ can be chosen to represent the failure surface. However, the condition that the failure surface be closed and symmetrical about the $\epsilon_6 = 0$ plane must be respected. A general function that satisfies these requirements is the following Fourier series representation:

$$h(\alpha, \phi) = 1 + \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^M (A_{mn} \cos n\alpha + B_{mn} \sin n\alpha) \cos(2m-1)\phi \quad (5)$$

where the constants A_{mn} and B_{mn} are to be determined to best describe the experimental data. The number of terms of the above series to be retained depends on the desired accuracy in properly describing the given failure surface. The coefficients A_{mn} and B_{mn} are computed using a least-squares technique.

Fig. 2 Parametric failure surface in three-dimensional strain space.

3. EXAMPLE OF APPLICATION OF THE NEW PARAMETRIC CRITERION

As an example of application, the experimental results presented by Rowlands *et al.* (7) for a paperboard will now be analysed using the present criterion. This paperboard is reported to be a unidirectionally reinforced material. The experimental data were presented by the authors in terms of stresses and at four shear stress levels: $\tau_{12} = 0.0, 6.9, 10.3,$ and 15.9 MPa. These results, including the elastic properties of the material, are listed in tabular form in the article by Rowlands *et al.* (7).

To apply the present *strain-based* criterion to paperboard, the stress data were transformed into strains assuming linear elastic response as follows:

$$\epsilon_i = S_{ij}\sigma_j \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 6) \quad (6)$$

where S_{ij} is the compliance tensor. Using the strain data so-obtained and taking $N = M = 3$ in Equation (5), the failure surface was obtained. The projection of this failure surface in the plane $\epsilon_6 = 0$ is depicted in Fig. 3. This series representation contains 18 constants, which are determined in a straightforward fashion using a least-squares fit. It can be observed in the figure that the proposed function describes the experimental results quite well.

Finally, a parametric function of the form (5) has been applied to the stress-based criterion, Equation (3). The results of the analysis with $N = M = 3$ are shown in Fig. 4, for the plane $\tau_{12} = 0$. Here again it can be observed that the experimental data are well described with this parametric form.

Fig. 3 Failure envelope for paperboard in strain space ($\epsilon_6 = 0$).

Fig. 4 Failure envelope for paperboard in stress space ($\tau_{12} = 0$).

4. CONCLUSION

The parametric criterion originally proposed by Labossière and Neale (5) in *stress space* has been extended to *strain space*. A function that satisfies all the requirements of symmetry and closure of the failure surface has been proposed in this study. The general applicability of the function was demonstrated in strain and stress spaces, and very good theoretical-experimental correlations were obtained. This parametric function thus furnishes a systematic approach for the description of failure surfaces for orthotropic fibre-reinforced laminae. Applications of this approach to other materials are currently being pursued.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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6. REFERENCES

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